

Linnæus University

Monthly Report March 2026

SENTINEL Wild Birds

Söderquist, P., Byrne, A., Lewis, N., van Toor, M. L., Waldenström, J., &
SENTINEL Wild Birds Consortium

CONTENTS

Summary report.....	3
1. Overview.....	3
2. Results.....	3
2.1 Data collection	3
2.2 Genomics summary	9
3. Conclusion.....	11
References.....	13
Acknowledgement	13

SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from five nodes, collected from January to March 2026.

Note that the numbers presented in this and previous monthly reports are based on data extracts prepared at the time of analysis. As some samples may be re-analysed or reported in more than one period, the numbers reported across different monthly summaries are not strictly additive and may differ slightly from aggregated totals in the underlying dataset.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 27th of February 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18799920>), and as of 15th March 2026, test results have been submitted for 1,937 samples taken from 916 individuals representing 32 taxa from five nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 1,937 collected samples, 728 (38%) were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 728 (38%) cloacal swabs, 292 (15%) feather swabs, 116 (6%) fecal samples, 59 (3%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 12 (<1%) pooled organs, and 2 (<1%) brain samples.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Mallard (260 individuals) and Eurasian Teal (172 individuals; Table 1). Highest bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 30 individuals was found in Great Crested Grebe (50%; n=44), Mallard (17%, n=260), Eurasian Coot (6%, n=34), Common Shelduck (4%, n=74), and Eurasian Teal (2%, n=172). Overall bird-level prevalence was 9% (84 of 916 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from January to March 2026.

Group/species	Node 3 Ukraine		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Germany		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 9 Spain		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																	
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Black Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Greater White-fronted Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	16	0	0%
Common Shelduck	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	2	0	0	74	3	4%
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Anas sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Mallard	124	44	81	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	26	0	28	1	260	45	17%
Domestic mallard	0	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	0	0%
Northern Pintail	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	9	1	11%
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Eurasian Wigeon	1	1	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	20	1	5%
Eurasian Teal	4	1	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	162	2	1	0	172	4	2%
Common Pochard	0	0	9	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	6	0	23	1	4%
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	5	0	0%
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	0	25	0	0%
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	10	2	20%
<i>Grebes</i>																	
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0%
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	44	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	22	50%
<i>Cormorants</i>																	
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0%
<i>Hérons, storks</i>																	
Eurasian Bittern	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Raptors</i>																	
Common Buzzard	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Rails</i>																	
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Eurasian Coot	14	2	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	2	0	34	2	6%
<i>Waders</i>																	
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
Common Snipe	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100%
<i>Larids</i>																	
Black-headed Gull	1	0	94	0	5	0	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	108	1	1%
Little Gull	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0%
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%
Caspian Gull	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	1	16	1	6%
Total	150	51	299	23	55	3	19	1	15	0	294	4	84	2	916	84	9%

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 120 (6%) tested positive for avian influenza virus, of which two (<0.1%) samples were positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI; H5N1) virus (Figure 1; Table 2). One originated from an adult female Eurasian Teal in Italy, sampled in February 2026, and one from a Great Crested Grebe in Georgia, sampled in February 2026.

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as authors. This task has been carried out exclusively by the author in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author, awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the author.

Other AIV detections

In addition to confirmed HPAI detections, several other avian influenza virus (AIV) positive samples were identified. Subtyped rRT-PCR-positive samples included one H5N1 (an adult female Tufted Duck sampled in Austria), which has not yet been tested for HPAI virus. Positive samples further included one H5N6 (a Great Crested Grebe from Georgia), 17 H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes (six female and five male Mallards, one female Northern Pintail, one Common Shelduck, one Eurasian Wigeon, and one Common Snipe; all from Ukraine, one Great Crested Grebe from Georgia, and one female Black-headed Gull from Austria). One adult female Eurasian Teal from Italy was also determined as H1N1 by Next Generation Sequencing.

FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 1,937 individuals sampled in Ukraine, Georgia, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from January to March 2026.

A weekly compilation of all 31,977 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to March 2026, can be seen in Figure 2. The proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, for all nodes combined, can be seen in Figure 3. Prevalence was relatively high during the autumn of 2025 and decreased after the turn of the year. In early 2026, prevalence values have been higher than those observed during the same period in 2025 (Figure 3).

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from January to March 2026.

Group/species	Node 3 Ukraine			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Germany			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI
<i>Waterfowl</i>																								
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Black Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Greater White-fronted Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0
Common Shelduck	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	216	2	0	0	0	0	220	4	0
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Anas sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Mallard	248	62	0	160	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	78	0	0	56	1	0	543	63	0
Domestic mallard	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0
Northern Pintail	4	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	24	1	0
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Eurasian Wigeon	2	2	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	35	2	0
Eurasian Teal	8	1	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	486	4	1	2	0	0	501	6	1
Common Pochard	0	0	0	18	2	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	12	0	0	46	2	0
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	10	0	0
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	0	0	50	0	0
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	12	2	0
<i>Grebes</i>																								
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	0	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	0	0
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	77	33	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	77	33	1
<i>Cormorants</i>																								
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0
<i>Hérons, storks</i>																								
Eurasian Bittern	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Raptors</i>																								
Common Buzzard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																								
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Eurasian Coot	28	2	0	18	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	4	0	0	75	2	0
<i>Waders</i>																								
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Common Snipe	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0
<i>Larids</i>																								
Black-headed Gull	2	0	0	112	0	0	5	0	0	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	127	1	0
Little Gull	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
Caspian Gull	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	2	0	32	2	0
Total	300	72	0	495	35	1	58	3	0	19	1	0	15	0	0	882	6	1	168	3	0	1937	120	2

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as authors. This task has been carried out exclusively by the author in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author, awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the author.

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 31,977 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at nine nodes between August 2024 and March 2026, yielding 2,268 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 98 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as authors. This task has been carried out exclusively by the author in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author, awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the author.

FIGURE 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and March 2026, separated for each year. The figures only include bird samples (excluding mussels and water samples). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as authors. This task has been carried out exclusively by the author in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author, awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the author.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 27th of February 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18799920>), and as of the 15th of March 2026, five new H5 sequences have been generated from samples positive for HPAI, all of which were of the H5N1 subtype, and includes the two samples described above, as well as three samples that were tested in a previous report. These samples were collected in Georgia (Node 4 Eastern Black Sea) and Italy (Node 7 Veneto Region). The samples from Georgia were collected from a Common Pochard, a Great-crested Grebe and two Mallards, whilst the sample from Italy was collected from a Eurasian Teal.

Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from these sequences found that all belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of HPAI (Figure 4A).

All five of the H5 HPAI sequences were classified as the DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>), and were found to be similar to other DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project (Figure 4B). The sequences from Node 4 Eastern Black Sea were similar to sequences collected in Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) as well as sequences from outside of SENTINEL Wild Birds project from: Belgium, England, Finland, Ireland, Norway, and The Netherlands (Figure 4C), whilst the sequence from Node 7 Veneto Region was similar to poultry sequences also from Italy (Figure 4D).

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Aside from the H5 sequences, there have been five non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Austria (Node 6 Lake Constance Region) and Italy (Node 7 Veneto Region). The sequence from Austria was generated from a faecal sample collected from a Eurasian Wigeon and was found to be of the HxN4, whilst the four sequences from Italy were all generated from samples collected from Eurasian Teal and were of the following subtypes: 1xH4N6, 1xH6N2, 1xH9N2, and 1xH9N3.

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) up to 17th March 2026, and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260319ho>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

FIGURE 4 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 4 Eastern Black Sea and Node 7 Veneto Region. A. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea, Node 4 Eastern Black Sea, Node 5 Wadden Sea, Node 7 Veneto Region and Node 8 Camargue Region in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. **C.** Further zoom image of the HA tree focussing on the H5 sequences from Node 4 Eastern Black Sea from this report and Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea from previous reports. **D.** Further zoom image of the HA tree focussing on the H5 sequence from Node 7 Veneto Region from this report. In **A**, **B**, **C** and **D** tip shapes are coloured according to the sampling node.

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as authors. This task has been carried out exclusively by the author in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author, awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the author.

3. CONCLUSION

As outlined in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project plan, sampling activities typically decrease during spring. Despite this seasonal reduction, a total of 1,937 samples from 916 individuals across more than 30 species in seven countries were collected during the current reporting period. This demonstrates that the geographical coverage of active avian influenza surveillance in wild birds in and near Europe remains high.

Based on samples collected between January and March 2026, the overall bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus was close to 10%, which is considerably higher than during the same period in 2025. It is also higher than in the most recent report and comparable to levels observed in January, which included a substantial proportion of samples from the autumn period. This suggests continued virus circulation following the large-scale outbreaks during autumn 2025. Such persistence may be facilitated by aggregation of waterfowl during late winter, which can sustain transmission even as the seasonal transition towards spring begins.

The observed prevalence was largely driven by Mallards, which showed a bird-level prevalence of 17%. This is consistent with the well-established role of Mallards as key reservoir hosts for avian influenza viruses in Europe. A notably higher prevalence was observed in Great Crested Grebes (50%), although based on a smaller sample size. Additional high prevalence values were observed in Tufted Duck (20%) and Common Snipe (100%), but these are based on very limited sample sizes and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

Only two individuals tested positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus during this reporting period: one adult female Eurasian Teal in Italy and one Great Crested Grebe in Georgia, both sampled in February 2026. Repeated detections of HPAI in Eurasian Teals in the Veneto region are consistent with previous findings within the project and support the role of this area as an important wintering hotspot for HPAI detection in migratory waterfowl. In contrast, the detection of HPAI in a Great Crested Grebe represents the first such case within the project. Notably, a total of 22 Great Crested Grebes tested positive for avian influenza virus in Georgia during February, indicating a localised increase in virus circulation in this species. Given that several grebe species overwinter in large numbers along the Black Sea coast, and that previous cases have been reported in grebes in the Black Sea region (Lewis *et al.* 2013; Muzyka *et al.* 2019), this observation highlights the importance of the region for avian influenza virus circulation across a broader range of aquatic bird species.

During this period, five H5 sequences have been generated, all of which were from the 2.3.4.4b HPAI clade and were confirmed to be the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA *et al.* 2025), and demonstrate high similarity to sequences collected across Europe, including other sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In addition to prior reports, this similarity highlights the connectivity between the active and passive sampling schemes that are ongoing within Europe. In Italy, the similarity between wild bird sequences and poultry-derived sequences suggests potential epidemiological links between wild and domestic transmission cycles.

In addition to the H5 sequences, one H5N6 virus, 17 H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes, and one H1N1 virus were identified across multiple species of waterfowl, one grebe, and one gull. These findings are consistent with previous SENTINEL Wild Birds reports and further support the presence of high subtype diversity of avian influenza viruses circulating in

wild bird populations. Such diversity provides opportunities for reassortment and highlights the dynamic nature of avian influenza virus evolution.

Overall, the results from this reporting period indicate continued circulation of avian influenza viruses in wild birds in and near Europe following the autumn 2025 outbreaks. Despite seasonal reductions in sampling intensity, prevalence remains relatively high compared to the same period in previous year. The epidemiological pattern is largely driven by waterfowl species, particularly Mallards, but detections in other species, such as grebes, underline the involvement of a broader range of aquatic birds. The limited number of HPAI detections, combined with genomic evidence of stable viral lineages, suggests ongoing but limited circulation. These findings emphasise the importance of continued surveillance during the transition from winter to spring, a period that may play a key role in maintaining virus circulation and facilitating its spread along migratory flyways.

REFERENCES

- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), EURL (European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza), Buczkowski H, Ducatez M, Fusaro A, Gonzales JL, Kuiken T, Mirinavičiūtė G, Ståhl K, Staubach C, Svartström O, Terregino C, Willgert K, Alarcón E, and Kohnle L. (2025). Avian influenza overview September–November 2025. *EFSA Journal*, 23(12).
<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2025.9834>
- Elbe, S. and Buckland-Merrett, G. (2017). Data, disease and diplomacy: GISAID's innovative contribution to global health. *Global Challenges*, 1:33-46.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.1018>
- Lewis, NS., Javakhishvili, Z., Russell, CA., Machabishvili, A., Lexmond, P., et al. (2013) Avian Influenza Virus Surveillance in Wild Birds in Georgia: 2009–2011. *PLoS ONE* 8(3): e58534.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0058534>
- Muzyka, D., Rula, O., Tkachenko, S., Muzyka, N., Köthe, S., et al. (2019). Highly pathogenic and low pathogenic avian influenza H5 subtype viruses in wild birds in Ukraine. *Avian diseases*, 63(1s), 235-245.
- Shu, Y. and McCauley, J. (2017). GISAID: from vision to reality. *EuroSurveillance*, 22(13).
<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2017.22.13.30494>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We gratefully acknowledge all data contributors, i.e., the Authors and their Originating laboratories responsible for obtaining the specimens, and their Submitting laboratories for generating the genetic sequence and metadata and sharing via the GISAID Initiative, on which this research is based.

Node 1: LABRIS, Riigi Laboriuuringute ja Riskihindamise Keskus (Estonia); Ruokavirasto, Finnish Food Authority (Finland); University of Turku (Finland)

Node 2: Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) (Sweden); Linnaeus University (Sweden); Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment "BIOR" (Latvia); National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute (Lithuania); State Food and Veterinary Service (Lithuania); National Veterinary Research Institute (Poland)

Node 3: Linnaeus University (Sweden); National Scientific Centre Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine (Kharkiv, Ukraine); State Research Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics and Veterinary and Sanitary Expertise (Kyiv, Ukraine)

Node 4: Centre of Wildlife Disease Ecology (CWDE), Ilia State University; State Laboratory of Agriculture of Georgia

Node 5: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (the Netherlands); Erasmus Medical Center (the Netherlands); Netherlands Institute of Ecology, Dutch Centre for Avian Migration and Demography (the Netherlands)

Node 6: Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) (Austria); Verein für die Betreuung des Naturschutzgebietes Rheindelta (Naturschutzverein Rheindelta) (Austria); Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute (FLI) (Germany); Max-Planck-Institut für Verhaltensbiologie (MPI) (Germany); National Reference Centre for Poultry and Rabbit Diseases (NRGK) (Switzerland); Swiss Institute for Virology and Immunology (IVI) (Switzerland)

Node 7: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie; Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA)

Node 8: École Nationale Vétérinaire de Toulouse (ENVT); INRAE (Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement); La Tour du Valat; Conservatoire d'Espaces Naturels d'Occitanie (CEN Occitanie); Laboratoire Départemental du Gard; Office Français de la Biodiversité (OFB); Ministère de l'Agriculture et de la Souveraineté Alimentaire; Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN); Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail (ANSES)

Node 9: Martina Ferraguti, Josué Martínez-de la Puente, and Jordi Figuerola at Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD-CSIC); Ursula Höfle at Grupo de Sanidad y Biotecnología (SaBio), Instituto de Investigación en Recursos Cinegéticos (IREC-CSIC); Elisa Pérez-Ramírez and Jovita Fernández-Pinero at Centro de Investigación en Sanidad Animal (CISA-INIA-CSIC) (Spain).